

Massive hemotransfusion in patients with critical blood loss

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Abstract

Transfusion medicine has undergone a long historical evolution—from early attempts at animal-to-animal transfusion through animal-to-human procedures to successful human-to-human transfusions following the discovery of blood groups. Today, it represents an independent field of medical science that supports key clinical specialties, such as surgery, traumatology, and obstetrics.

Massive blood loss is defined as bleeding at a rate of 150 mL/min, while massive transfusion refers to the administration of 10 or more units of blood within 24 h. In contemporary practice, transfusion medicine faces significant challenges related to the declining number of donors, increasing morbidity, population aging, and the emergence of new infections.

Reducing the number of transfusions per patient requires an optimized preoperative assessment of bleeding risk. Ensuring an adequate preoperative blood volume, early diagnosis and correction of anemia, and management of preoperative coagulopathy may limit intraoperative and postoperative bleeding and decrease the need for large-volume blood transfusion.

This study supports the need for restrictive transfusion strategies and highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to preoperative preparation and therapy aimed at reducing the number of transfusions per patient.

Keywords

Blood transfusion, donor, massive transfusion, transfusion medicine

Introduction

Blood is a vital resource obtained exclusively through donation. It has no substitute, possesses high biological value, and is available only in limited quantities. Against the backdrop of increasing medical needs, rising demand for blood and blood components, and an aging population in Bulgaria, the management of this resource and the provision of sufficient blood supplies represent a significant challenge, particularly in cases of acute bleeding and massive blood loss.

The classical definition of massive transfusion was introduced during the Vietnam War and refers to the administration of 10 units of blood within a 24 h period, with its main limitation being dependence on the patient's survival throughout those 24 h (Moore and Raval 2022). A universally accepted definition of "massive hemotransfusion" is lacking. In practice, dynamic criteria are also used, taking into account not only the volume but also the rate of blood loss—replacement of 50% of the circulating volume within 3 h and blood loss of 150 mL/min or 1.5 mL/kg/min for ≥ 20 min (Rutledge et al. 1986).

Globally, more than 100 million units of red blood cell concentrate are transfused annually, underscoring the importance of effective transfusion strategies and the safety of blood products (Bruun Rasmussen et al. 2022).

Coagulopathy in massive blood loss is a multifactorial event. It may result from hemodilution, hypothermia, acidosis, consumption of coagulation factors, or medication effects. As emphasized by Kozek Langenecker (2007), the management of massive intraoperative blood loss requires simultaneous correction of hemodynamics, coagulation, and metabolic disturbances.

Massive hemotransfusions are required in fields such as traumatology, surgery, and obstetrics and gynecology. Postpartum hemorrhage is a leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide (Khan et al. 2006; Thurn et al. 2019).

Massive bleeding may be anticipated—for example, during major surgical procedures with a high risk of blood loss—or unexpected. The primary problem may be surgical or related to disorders of hemostasis, and bleeding may be localized or systemic.

Preoperative risk assessment and understanding the pathophysiology of massive bleeding are crucial for clinical outcomes. Replacement therapy with blood and blood components is applied, including red blood cell concentrate, fresh frozen plasma (FFP), platelet concentrate, coagulation factors (prothrombin complex, fibrinogen), antifibrinolytics, and local hemostatic agents (Kozek Langenecker 2007).

Ensuring adequate preoperative blood volume is essential for minimizing intraoperative and postoperative complications. Anemia should be identified and treated as early as possible before surgery.

Preoperative coagulopathy, whether due to anticoagulant therapy or perioperative coagulation disorders, is a significant risk factor for perioperative blood loss. Coagulopathy affects intraoperative hemodynamics, the volume of blood loss, and the need for transfusion. Differentiating pre-existing hemostatic abnormalities and understanding the dynamic changes in coagulation during surgery are necessary for safe patient management.

The concept of blood use focuses on the prevention, diagnosis, and timely treatment of the causes of anemia and coagulopathies, with the aim of minimizing transfusion and improving safety and clinical outcomes.

Aim

To define the frequency, risk factors, and patient characteristics associated with massive blood transfusions. To compare the traditional definition of massive transfusion, i.e., administration of 10 units of blood within 24 h, with smaller-volume transfusions and to evaluate their impact on clinical outcomes in the context of restrictive versus liberal transfusion therapy.

Materials and methods

The study was retrospective and covered a 3-year period—2021, 2022, and 2023. It was conducted in a large multidisciplinary hospital for active treatment, comprising surgical and therapeutic departments: general and vascular surgery, traumatology, obstetrics and gynecology, gastroenterology, and units with high consumption of blood and blood components.

The number of hemotransfused patients during the study period was determined, and they were divided into three groups:

1. Patients who received one or more units of red blood cell concentrate (RBC) during their hospital stay, but not within a 24 h period.
2. Patients who received three or more units of RBC within 24 h, subdivided into:
 - Patients who received exactly 3 units/24 h.
 - Patients who received more than 3 and up to 9 units/24 h.
3. Patients who received 10 or more units of RBC within 24 h.

Results

The total number of hemotransfused patients during the 3-year study period was 1661. All of them received one or more units of red blood cell concentrate (RBC) during their hospital stay.

Seventy patients received three or more units of RBC within 24 h. Among them, bleeding was controlled with the transfusion of 3 units in 47 patients. In 23 patients, transfusion of up to 9 units of RBC within 24 h was required. No cases of transfusion of 10 or more units of RBC within 24 h were recorded.

The distribution of transfused patients who received three or more units of RBC within 24 h across clinical specialties was as follows: 44 surgery patients, 15 traumatology patients, and 11 obstetrics and gynecology patients. The largest proportion of patients was observed in the surgical departments, which is explained by the wide spectrum of pathologies managed in these units—abdominal, vascular, purulent-septic, and thoracic surgery. These clinical fields are associated with an increased risk of acute blood loss and a corresponding need for transfusion therapy.

In 2021, a total of 529 patients received hemotransfusions. Of these, 517 patients (97.7%) were transfused with up to 2 units of RBC, eight patients (1.5%) received 3 units, and four patients (0.8%) received between 3 and 9 units of RBC.

In 2022, a total of 536 patients received hemotransfusions. Of these, 509 patients (95%) were transfused with up to 2 units of RBC, 18 patients (3.4%) received 3 units, and nine patients (1.7%) received between 3 and 9 units of RBC.

In 2023, a total of 596 patients received hemotransfusions. Of these, 565 patients (95%) were transfused with up to 2 units of RBC, 21 patients (3.5%) received 3 units, and 10 patients (1.7%) received between 3 and 9 units of RBC.

The results are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Number of hemotransfused patients over the 3-year study period.

The data allow comparison of transfusion activity between years and outline a stable profile of patients receiving up to 2 units of erythrocyte concentrate, as well as a relatively low frequency of cases with transfusions of 3 to 9 units. Fig. 2 presents a summary distribution of blood transfusions in the period 2021–2023 according to the number of transfused units of erythrocyte concentrate.

Figure 2. Distribution of blood transfusions (2021–2023) by number of transfused erythrocyte concentrate units.

The comparative analysis across the 3 years shows an increase in the number of patients who received hemotransfusion, while the percentage distribution according to the volume of transfused blood remained stable throughout the period (Kozek Langenecker 2007). A consistent trend toward restrictive transfusion therapy was observed, in which the administration of 1 or 2 units of RBC was sufficient to control blood loss in the majority of patients.

Discussion

Following restrictive transfusion strategies, in which the threshold for administering RBC is a hemoglobin level of 70 g/L, most patients receive 1 or 2 units of RBC. This approach aligns with contemporary recommendations aimed at limiting unnecessary transfusions and minimizing their associated risks.

Optimization of hemostasis—including timely correction of coagulation abnormalities and the use of minimally invasive surgical techniques—contributes to reducing the need for hemotransfusion (Neveleff et al. 2010; Nikolouzakis et al. 2025). Multidisciplinary teams consisting of a surgeon, transfusion hematologist, and anesthesiologist play a key role in assessing and managing patients at risk of bleeding, ensuring coordinated and timely therapy.

The use of data from personal and electronic health records, as well as integrated laboratory systems, enables more precise patient assessment and better planning of transfusion strategies. Comprehensive evaluation of the clinical condition, accurate determination of indications for hemotransfusion, minimization of intra- and postoperative blood loss, and optimization of hematologic parameters in the preoperative period lead to a substantial reduction in the need for allogeneic blood. This, in turn, decreases healthcare costs related to hospital stays and the provision of blood products.

Conclusion

Despite the applied strategies and the reduced need for large-volume transfusions per patient, the total number of transfused blood units continues to increase. The number of patients requiring transfusions of 1 to 3 units of blood is also rising.

With the global aging of the population, the demand for transfusions in oncology patients, individuals on hemodialysis, those undergoing interventional cardiology procedures, transplantation, and joint replacement continues to grow, necessitating substantial quantities of blood (AABB 2014).

The development of new methods and approaches to donor recruitment, along with the promotion of voluntary, non-remunerated blood donation, represents an essential strategy for ensuring an adequate supply of blood and blood products.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: EK-03-26/07.04.2026 from UMHATEM “N. I. Pirogov” – Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: UMHATEM “N. I. Pirogov” – Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.